

Student Personnel Services and Sustainable Secondary Education in South-West Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined student personnel services and sustainable secondary education in Southwest Nigeria. Four null hypotheses were generated to guide the study. A descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The study sampled 900 respondents from four selected states in Southwest, Nigeria. The selected states are Ekiti, Ondo, Ogun, and Osun states using a proportional sampling technique. 'The Student Personnel Services Questionnaire' (SPSQ) and 'Sustainable Secondary Education Questionnaire' (SSEQ) were self-designed data collection instruments for the study. Experts in Test and Measurements and Educational management at Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology and Ekiti State University validated the instrument. The instruments reliability was tested using test-retest method and coefficient values of 0.82 and 0.71 were obtained respectively for SPSQ and SSEQ. Student personnel services of functional library, healthcare services, and sports and recreational activities have significant relations on sustainable secondary Education. It was recommended that the government should ensure that functional library services, health care services and sports and recreational activities are provided to provoke students' knowledge and skills for positive productivity as a tool for sustainable secondary education in Southwest, Nigeria.

Keywords: *Students, Secondary Education, Sustainable, Library, Healthcare, Sports.*

INTRODUCTION

Secondary education is critical in bridging Nigeria's primary and tertiary education levels of education. Oyeleye (2019) opined that secondary Education is the second level of education in Nigeria headed by a school administrator called principal. It is a collective education designed to develop young people's abilities, attitudes, and overall brilliance for them to integrate into the society in which they live. According to FRN (2004), the government created secondary education to achieve several goals, including raising a generation of young people who can think independently, respect the feelings of others, and value the principles outlined in the broad national goals.

Sustainability in this study refers to secondary school system ability to persevere, particularly in this period of growing global competition, while leveraging resource replenishment to the maximum. Sustainable secondary education is the process of preparing students for the workforce and life in a way that safeguards the socioeconomic well-being of the present without jeopardizing the future. The ability of secondary schools to persist and remain current is relevant. Additionally, it is the process by which the use of student personnel services, the concentration of financial support on the provision of these services, and

institutional adjustments all collaborate to better both the present and potential future capacities to meet the needs and aspirations of students.

All services offered to students to advance their education outside the typical classroom curriculum are referred to as student personnel services (Okonkwo and Obineli, 2013). Haruna (2008) reviewed that the services provided to secondary school students for the accomplishment of academic goals other than those covered by the regular curriculum are referred to student personnel services. The schools' oversight of student personnel enables them to provide personal and group therapy, as well as follow-up support. It is an essential component of secondary school administration. It seeks to guide students to facilitate their adjustment to school life and progress them toward self-awareness and self-realization. By managing the student personnel service well, secondary education can be sustained in Southwest Nigeria. The low academic performance of some students in the classroom and on standardized examinations suggested that these students' attitudes have negative impacts on secondary education standards in Southwest Nigeria. Numerous students were involved in examination malpractices and also engaged in other violations on standardized examinations like WAEC, JAMB, and NECO. The state government's struggle to maintain a uniform secondary school system appeared to be exacerbated by poor student personnel services. To ensure that the students receive a high-quality education in a supportive environment, it is the responsibility of the school administration to provide the necessary facilities for the students. Observation revealed that several secondary schools in the Southwest without student personnel service appeared to have problems with disruptions and misbehaviour from students, such as stealing, using drugs, scamming, truancy, delinquency, intimidation, assessment fraud, zealotry, showing up late to class, and moral laziness.

However, some principals show non-challant attitude towards providing adequate resources for personnel services in their schools. This is in line with Adu, Adesua and Familugba (2014) that school heads must provide adequate resources in order to promote effective teaching and learning in their schools. Sub-variables of student personnel services such as functional libraries, healthcare service and the provision of sports and recreational activities must be provided. These were specifically investigated. The researchers discovered that many secondary school libraries in Southwest Nigeria lacked the necessary facilities to function properly. Some libraries, for example, were obsolete, on the verge of collapse, and devoid of current materials and other valuable resources. This impeded the achievement of high secondary education standards in Southwest, Nigeria. Barrat and Barrat (2009) also acknowledged that international research was widely available in African libraries, despite being out of date and unrelated to students' informational needs and interests. Furthermore, sections of some libraries in Southwest secondary schools are occasionally modified to classrooms or spaces for workers' meetings without regard for if such conversions are conducive to studying. Most school libraries are devoid of tables, chairs, fans, shelves, and other amenities. The lack of these facilities continues to have an impact on the sustainability of secondary education in Southwest Nigeria. According to Percy-Smith (2009), to achieve sustainability in secondary education, schools should use functional and innovative learning approaches that enable students to act on their knowledge of sustainable lifestyles.

Healthcare services are required for students to be diligent, ingenious, and observant to improve their learning. Students should have access to quality health care to achieve excellent academic results and enhance long-term development in secondary schools. Students must maintain their psychological and physical well-being. According to Adeola (2014), Nigerian

students are constantly vulnerable to risks and hazards at school, making the process of learning complicated. All attempts in Nigeria to address the issue of a school health initiative have largely remained at the policy level, with little implementation. When a student is healthy, he can take a proactive role in his studying. Tension, nervousness, panic, trauma, distress, or physical health issues, on the other hand, assert to be barriers to their academic success. In addition, Rochmes (2016) opined that health and education are inextricably linked, and studies show that unhealthy students are less capable of learning. Oduntan (2006) also observed that the school health programme was functional at the onset but started declining in the late eighties. This may be due to the economic downturn, political instability, and corruption in recent decades. Providing health care services for secondary schools students help to promote educational goals which can lead to sustainable educational system, improving health of the students, and also enhance opportunities to learn.

The need to provide sports and recreational activities for secondary school students cannot be overemphasised. Students' educational goals and academic performance cannot be achieved solely through classroom instruction alone. Out-of-classroom activities or learning opportunities such as sports and games, as well as other social services, must be included in the education programme. Due to their intellectual benefits, sports and recreational activities for students have become an essential and integral component of the curriculum at all levels of education. According to Charles (2016), sports and recreational activities contribute to the creation of a healthy learning environment that promotes students' intellectual, affective, and locomotor activity growth. The problem of the study is therefore to investigate students' personnel service in relation to sustainable secondary education in Southwest Nigeria.

Akinnubi and Kayode (2012) asserted that student personnel services are welfare services offered in educational institutions to stop the needless rises in anti-social behaviour among students and to enhance optimistic reasoning and deeds that would help them achieve their academic goals and potential career preferences. Oboegbulem (2004) cited the relevance of students' personnel service in helping students think clearly, express their opinions and improve their skills to make wise decisions. It is a crucial part of the operations and services important to secondary school administration. Nevertheless, student disturbances and misconduct have risen over time in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria; this circumstance can point to a concern with the way student personnel services are being carried out. Secondary schools have been labelled unproductive due to several problems both inside and outside the educational system (Otomewo, 2011). According to Roseline (2015), student personnel services are intended to help students with an orientation to make the transition to school life easier, provide financial aid, health and safety services, food and a conducive hostel for boarding students, a variety of co-curricular activities, and recommend the appropriate disciplinary measures to the school administration. Given the foregoing, efficient administration of the secondary school's student personnel services may significantly contribute to maintaining the preservation of high standards of instruction in secondary schools in southwest Nigeria.

Ogbuji (2009) conducted research on the assessment of student personnel services in Cross River state secondary schools. The study's sample included 327 principals and 692 teachers. Data for the study were gathered using a formalized 52-item questionnaire and a 30-item checklist. The study's findings are as follows: an orientation programme is implemented in secondary schools in Cross River state, effective health care services and civic amenities are lacking, students partake in co-curricular activities and in school administration, the findings showed that there is a significant difference in the providing of student personnel services in

secondary schools in the state and there is no significant difference among the three groups of schools on the constraints to the provision of student personnel services in secondary schools in Cross River state. Amaizu (2003) investigated methods for improving student personnel services in secondary schools in the Onitsha Education Zone. Mean scores were used to answer research questions, and t-test statistics were used to test null hypotheses. According to the researcher, methods to be implemented to improve student personnel services include: the emergence of guidance and counselling services in all schools in the zone, the renovation of the boarding system in secondary schools, adequate school funding, the posting of medical personnel to all schools to cater for their health needs, recreation activities and active participation of the PTA in school funding, and active community involvement.

Adeoye (2014) investigated the effects of school libraries on students' academic achievement. The findings revealed that, in the majority of cases, learning achievement is dependent on the student's use of the library and positive study habits. Similarly, Smith (2011) conducted a study in which the learning outcomes of students who regularly use libraries were compared to those who do not use libraries and discovered that students who regularly read and conduct research in libraries performed better than those who do not or use the library occasionally. As a result, for long-term education, the government should make appropriate library supply in all secondary schools in the Southwest.

Adolescents who participate in extracurricular activities are reported to achieve higher grades in their academic performance, according to studies conducted by Darling, Caldwell, and Smith (2005) and Bashir and Hussain (2012). Furthermore, they have more positive attitudes toward school and higher academic goals. According to Roger (2005), recreation provides a channel for excess energy to be channeled into socially acceptable activities that meet individual and societal needs without the need for coercion, while also providing satisfaction and pleasure to people involved. We understand that engaging in recreational activities actually creates energy and enthusiasm, which leads to fulfillment and an optimistic mindset.

The study problem

Observation showed that some schools prepare well developed curriculum, but neglect some personnel services that could promote its effective implementation. Many Students have no access to some activities that could make them balanced products after the school life. Some schools do not have health care facilities while there are no room for extracurricular activities because of lack of facilities. Some students do not annex their potentials because of lack of provision in their schools. Many children with health challenges grow up with helmets when such are not looked into at the secondary school level when they are younger. Some secondary schools' managements fail to guide students to facilitate their adjustment to school life and progress them toward self-awareness and self-realization. Based on these problems, the researchers were set to assess student personnel services and sustainable secondary education in South-West Nigeria.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the objectives of the study:

1. To examine student personnel services and sustainable secondary education in Southwest, Nigeria.
2. To examine functional libraries and sustainable secondary education in Southwest Nigeria.
3. To investigate healthcare service and sustainable education in southwest Nigeria
4. To determine sport and recreational service and sustainable secondary education in southwest Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. Does functional library improve sustainable education in Southwest, Nigeria?
2. What are the perceptions of the teachers on the provision of health services for students in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria?
3. What are the opinions of the teachers on sport and recreational services in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between student personnel service and sustainable secondary education in Southwest Nigeria
2. There is no significant relationship between functional libraries and sustainable secondary education in Southwest, Nigeria
3. There is no significant relationship between healthcare services and sustainable secondary education in Southwest Nigeria.
4. There is no significant relationship between the provision of sports and recreational services and sustainable secondary education in Southwest Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The research design was descriptive because it involved the collection of data to describe the existing situation concerning student personnel services and sustainable secondary education in Southwest, Nigeria. It was also a survey design study because it selected and studied a sample chosen from a large population from where inferences were drawn about the features of the chosen population.

The population of the study included all 84,420 teachers in all 2,506 public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. While, the study's sample size comprised 900 teachers. A multistage sampling procedure was used to select the sample. Four states which are Ekiti, Ondo, Ogun and Osun states were selected from the six states in Southwest, Nigeria using a simple random sampling technique of balloting for the study. 5 public secondary schools from Ekiti state, 8 schools from Ondo state, 9 schools from Ogun state and 8 schools from Osun

state were selected for this study; while, 159 teachers were also selected from Ekiti state, 236 teachers from Ondo state, 253 from Ogun state and 250 teachers from Osun state. All were selected using proportional sampling technique.

The research instruments used for data collection were self-designed questionnaire titled ‘Student Personnel Service Questionnaire’(SPSQ) and ‘Sustainable Secondary Education Questionnaire’ (SSEQ). The SPSQ was in two sections: Section A contained personal information of teachers, while section B elicited the items of the questionnaire. There were 15 questions in section B which were arranged in three clusters. The teachers responded to the questionnaire on four (4) points Likert scale size as follows: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1).

Experts in the area of Test and Measurement and Departments of Educational Management determined the face and content validity of the instrument. Corrections were made based on their observation and recommendation. The reliability coefficient was obtained using the test-retest method of reliability and co-efficients of 0.82 and 0.71 were obtained respectively for SPSQ and SSEQ.

The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant.

RESULTS

Research Question: Does functional library improve sustainable Education in Southwest, Nigeria

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation on how functional libraries improve sustainable Education in Southwest, Nigeria.

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Availability of audio and visual resources students’ academic performance.	3.01	2.02	Agreed
2	Support and enhance educational goals	3.16	2.14	Agreed
3	Develop information literate students who are responsible in the society.	3.30	2.64	Agreed
4	Functional libraries focus on supporting and advancing students learning.	3.12	2.47	Agreed
5	Provide access to resources that expose learners to diverse ideas.	3.48	2.20	Agreed
	Average	3.21	2.29	Agreed

Table I presents how functional libraries improves sustainable education in Southwest, Nigeria. The mean rating score for the questionnaire is 2.50. The table showed that items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 scores are above the mean rating score of 2.50, implying their agreement with the statements. The average mean is 3.21; which also means that functional libraries improved sustainable Education in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What are the perceptions of teachers on provision of health services in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 2: Perceptions of the teachers on the provision of health services for students in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	Availability of health care center in the school	2.37	1.24	Disagreed
2.	Provision of first aid equipment	2.76	1.57	Agreed
3.	Routine medical screening of students	2.21	1.01	Disagreed
4.	Free health service for students.	2.51	1.30	Agreed
5.	Visual test for students	2.34	1.07	Disagreed
	Average	2.44	1.24	Disagreed

Table 2 presents the perceptions of teachers on the provision of health services for students in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The mean rating score for the questionnaire is 2.50. The table showed that items 1, 3 and 5 scores are below the mean score of 2.50, which means their disagreement with the statements. While, items 2 and 4 mean scores are above 2.50, implying agreement with the items. The average mean is 2.33; therefore, this showed that there is inadequate provision of health services for students in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Question 3: What are the opinions of the teachers on sport and recreational services in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 3: Teachers opinions on sport and recreational services in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria.

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	Students participate in physical activities in the school	3.43	2.21	Agreed
2.	Every student belongs to extracurricular activities	3.48	2.26	Agreed
3.	Adequate provision of recreational facilities	3.44	2.24	Agreed
4.	Students weekly participate in sport activities.	3.41	2.20	Agreed
5.	Availability of sport equipment.	2.86	2.31	Agreed
	Average	3.32	2.24	Agreed

Table 3 presents the opinions of the teachers on sport and recreational services in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The mean rating score for the questionnaire is 2.50. The table showed that items 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 scores are above the mean score of 2.50, which means their agreement with the statements. The average mean is 3.32; this means that the availability of sport and recreational services in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria is high.

Hypotheses testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between student personnel services and sustainable secondary Education.

Table 4: Relationship between student personnel services and sustainable secondary Education

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	p-value
Students personnel Services	900	44.88	28.88		
Sustainable secondary Education	900	25.59	5.92	0.510*	0.001

*P<0.05

Table 4 revealed that r-cal value of 0.510 was significant at 0.05 because P-value (0.001) < 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. As a result, there is a significant relationship between student personnel services and sustainable secondary education. This means that student personnel services are significantly related to sustainable secondary education.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between functional libraries and sustainable secondary education in Southwest, Nigeria.

Table 5: Relationship between Functional library and sustainable secondary Education

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	p-value
Functional library	900	16.62	11.22		
Sustainable secondary				0.326	0.010
Education	900	25.59	5.92		

*P<0.05

Table 5 showed that r-cal value of 0.326 was significant at 0.05 because P-value (0.010) < 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. As a result, there is a significant relationship between functional library and sustainable secondary education. This means that functional library significantly related to sustainable secondary education.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between healthcare services and sustainable secondary education in Southwest Nigeria.

Table 6: Relationship between Healthcare Services and Sustainable Secondary Education.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	p-value
Healthcare Services	900	12.19	6.19		
Sustainable secondary				0.340	0.011
Education	900	25.59	5.92		

*P<0.05

Table 6 showed that r-cal value of 0.340 was significant at 0.05 because P-value (0.011) < 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. As a result, there is a significant relationship between healthcare services and sustainable secondary education. This means that provision of healthcare services significantly related to sustainable secondary education.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between provision of sports and recreational services and sustainable secondary education in Southwest Nigeria.

Table 7: Relationship between the Provision of Sport and Recreational Services and Sustainable Education.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	p-value
Sport and recreational activities	900	16.62	11.22		
Sustainable secondary				0.401*	0.001
Education	900	25.59	5.92		

*P<0.05

Table 7 revealed that r-cal value of 0.401 was significant at 0.05 because P-value (0.001) < 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. As a result, there is a significant relationship between sports and recreational activities and sustainable secondary education. This means that sports and recreational services significantly related to sustainable secondary education.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding revealed that student personnel services significantly correlated with sustainable secondary education. The findings also showed that functional library, healthcare services and sports and recreational services significantly correlate with sustainable secondary education. The positive nature of the correlation coefficients showed that the more library services are provided in secondary schools, the higher the level of sustainable secondary education.

This implied that the provision of functional libraries, healthcare services and sports and recreational services help to provoke students' knowledge and skills for positive productivity as a tool for sustainable secondary education.

These services are also needed to enable individual students to develop their full potential and widen their horizons of perception, interests and skills among others, for sustainable secondary education. These findings proved that the availability and management of all these services are necessary for sustainable secondary education in Southwest, Nigeria.

The finding on functional libraries is in line with the assertion of Ijatuyi and Adebayo (2006), who summed up the need for library services for sustainable secondary education when they observed that, if education is to have a greater share in the moulding and building of a happier individual and a better society, the providers of education must go beyond their roles as literacy facilitators to a more practical role of providing libraries for sustaining the newly acquired skills of students in schools.

However, the finding on the provision of healthcare services in this study was- at variance with the work of Rochmes (2016) which posited that Health and Education are reciprocally related. The provision of Health care services for secondary school students helps to promote educational goals by increasing access to services, improving health, and enhancing opportunities to learn.

The result is also supported by Akpan (2016) who opined that sports and recreational activities help to create a healthy learning environment that promotes students' cognitive, affective and psychomotor development.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it could be concluded that student personnel services significantly relate to sustainable secondary education in Southwest, Nigeria. This emphasizes the need for functional library services, provision of healthcare services and sports and recreational services to be given serious attention by secondary schools management in all the states in Southwest, Nigeria. This implies that the more student personnel services are provided in secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria, the higher the level of sustainable secondary education.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of the study, it was recommended that:

- The government should ensure that adequate functional library services are provided to provoke students' knowledge and skills for positive productivity as a tool for sustainable secondary education in Southwest, Nigeria.
- Additionally, the school administrators should also ensure the provision of health care services for secondary school students to promote educational goals by improving health.
- The school programmes should also include sports and recreational activities to create a healthy learning environment that promotes students' cognitive, affective and psychomotor development.

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